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CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR

Miss Harsha .B. Pipalia

Ph.d (pursuing)

Saurashtra University, India

Under the guidance: Dr. J.M.Jani

ABSTRACT

Objective- The preceding historical perspective shows that successful companies adapt to changing consumer needs and environmental trends. The late 1990s and early 2000s have seen equally important consumer behaviour trends that influence marketing strategies. The main objective of studying consumer behaviour is to understand behaviour of a consumer as we all are consumers. It is essential for marketers to understand consumer to survive and succeed in these competitive environment because it is importance in day to day life which pertinence to decision making for their purchases. Secondly to study consumer attitude and various factors influencing their buying decision. In other words Consumer behaviour is a study of how individuals make decision to spend their available resources (time, money and effort) or consumption related aspects (What they buy? When they buy? How they buy? etc.). The heterogeneity among people makes understanding consumer behaviour a challenging task to marketers. Hence marketers felt the need to obtain an in-depth knowledge of consumers buying behaviour. Finally this knowledge acted as an imperative tool in the hands of marketers to forecast the future buying behaviour of customers and devise four marketing strategies in order to satisfy and retaining customers.

Design / Methodology/ Approach-The present research paper is conceptualized and is based on secondary data collected from reference books. In order to enhance the knowledge about study of consumer behaviour various model are studied.

Findings- Imperative tool and effective marketing strategies are needed for marketer to forecast the future buying behaviour of customer. By implementing various tools and strategies marketer can face the market competition and can achieve all the heights of success

Limitations-Present research is conceptualized and based on secondary data; research could have been more authenticated if it would have been based on primary data

Practical implications-This paper can inspire marketer, businessman and experts of their fields for bringing certain changes in their strategies for better future by adopting changes in business environment.

Originality/Value- The paper includes examples of consumer buying decision with different stages. Various models of a consumer behaviour help in understanding their decision making process.

Key words: consumer behaviour, marketing strategy and business environment, consumer buying decision.

INTRODUCTION

A word is due here to properly understand the term **consumer**. Consumer is a broad term and any person who uses a product or services or deals with it can be called a consumer. It is not necessary that the person should be a buyer of the product or service. The term consumer should not be confused with the word ‘customer’ which has the limited meaning of usually denoting a person who contracts to buy the product.

Personal consumers are those individual and households who themselves consumer goods or services.

An institutional consumer on the other hand is businesses, organization and groups that buy and consumers goods and services during the course of their operation.

CUSTOMERS VERSUS CONSUMERS

The term ‘customer’ is specific in terms of brand, company, or shop. It refers to person who customarily or regularly purchases particular brand, purchases a particular company’s product, or purchases from a particular shop. Thus a person who shops at Bata Stores or who uses Raymond’s clothing is a customer of these firms. Whereas the ‘consumer’ is a person who generally engages in the activities-search, select, use and dispose of products, services, experience, or ideas.

CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR

The term “customer” is typically used to refer to someone who regularly purchases from a particular store or company. The term “consumer” more generally refers to anyone engaging defined in terms of a specific firm while a consumer is not.

The term consumer behavior described two different kinds of consuming entities; the personal consumer and organizational consumer. The personal consumer buys goods and services his or her own use, for the use of household, or as a gift for a friend. In each of these contexts, the products are bought for final use by individual, who are referred to as end users or ultimate consumers.

The organizational consumers- include profit and not-for- profit businesses, government agencies, and institution, all of which must buy products, equipment, and services in order to run their organization.

Consumer behavior can be defined as the sum total of how individual and groups recognize and determine their need and how they purchase and experience goods and services to meet those needs. It include the ‘what-where-why-when-and –how” of the purchase and experience process. The study of consumer behavior investigates and develops methods to quantify, forecast and influence the behavior of consumers.

It is mainly the study of individuals, or organizations and the processes consumers use to search, select, use and dispose of products, services, experience, or ideas to satisfy needs and its impact on the consumer and the society.

IMPORTANCE OF CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR

Consumer behavior involves the psychological processes that consumer go through in recognizing needs, finding ways to solve these needs, making purchase decision, interpret information, makes plan, and implement these plans.

The consumer faces numerous sources of influence. Often, we take cultural influences for granted, but they are significant. Physical factor also influence our behaviour. We are more likely to buy soft drink when we are thirsty, for example food manufacturers found that it is more effective to advertise their products on the radio in the late afternoon when people are getting hungry.

Social factors also influence what consumer buy-often, consumers seek to imitate others whom they admire, and may buy the same brand.

Social environment can include both the mainstream culture and a subculture. Finally consumer behavior influenced by learning-you try a hamburger and learn that it satisfies your

hunger and taste good, and the next time you are hungry, you may consider another hamburger.

APPLICATION OF CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR KNOWLEDGE

From the marketing point of view, understanding consumer behavior is crucial to successful place. Some of the marketing application areas of consumer behavior knowledge include:

Market –Opportunity Analysis

Target-Market selection

Marketing- mix determination

Marketing strategy

Social marketing

Market-opportunity analysis, this involves examining trends and condition in the marketplace to identify consumer's needs and wants that are not being fully satisfied.

Target –market selection, this has to do with identifying distinct grouping of consumer who has unique wants and needs. Marketing- mix determination, this involves developing and implementing a strategy for delivering an effective combination of want-satisfying features to consumers within target market.

Marketing strategy, understanding of consumer behavior is needed in strategic marketing activities. This is because marketing straggles and tactics are based on explicit or implicit beliefs about consumer behavior.

Social marketing also require an in depth understanding of consumer and their behaviors' or attitudes. Social marketing is the application of marketing strategies and tactics to alter or create behaviors that have individuals and or society as a whole.

The study of consumer behavior can be approach in three different perspectives, consumer behavior is said to be of particular interest to influence or change that behaviour, including those primary concern is marketing,

Marketers study the behavior of consumers and use the finding in the following three principal ways:

1. Consumer behaviour studies help marketers understand the rationale for the behaviour of consumers and their real needs. Products and services are designed by marketers to meet these real needs.
2. Consumer research studies help research and forecast the behaviour and response of consumers to existing as well as proposed new products. They help to build profiles of consumers who are likely to use the product.
3. Consumer behaviour studies help to segment the marketers can address different consumer segment with different products and formulate suitable strategies. Marketers also obtain clues here as to how to motivate the target customer and most importantly bring in product innovations.

IMPLICATION FOR CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR

The shift to a more consumer-driven orientation is still going on today. Avon products reflect this shift. Before 1980, the company's sales-oriented management failed to see the potential impact of an increasing proportion of working women on its primary means of distribution-door-to-door sales of cosmetics.

The shift to a consumer orientation required a new management team, which promptly commissioned a large-scale study of women's cosmetic needs and attitudes towards Avon products. Avon's 2000 marketing campaign, 'let's Talk', was its first global marketing campaign. The goal of the campaign, accordingly to the then-new CEO, Andrea Jung, was to build on Avon's brand image and to update its door-to-door sales strategy to make it more contemporary for modern women. Avon has also extended its brand through its web site, which offers convenient online shopping and product information, as an extension of this strategy, Avon plans to launch a new global operation aimed at teenage girls in 2003. The plan is to use teens on a worldwide basis to sell beauty products to other teens through the web, direct selling, and catalogs.

It is possible through only changing marketing operation:

- By providing a spur to consumer behaviour research.
- By creating a more customer-oriented framework for marketing strategies.
- By encouraging measurement of the factors that influence consumer to purchase.
- By emphasizing market segmentation.
- By emphasizing product positioning to meet consumer needs.

- By focusing more on the individual consumer.

Marketing management has recognized that the determinants of consumer behaviour have a direct bearing on the formulation of marketing strategies.

NEED FOR STUDY OF CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR

The study of consumer behaviour helps everything as all are consumers. It is essential for marketers to understand consumer to survive and succeed in these competitive environment. The following reasons highlight the importance of studying consumer behaviour as a discipline.

- **importance in day to day life**
- **pertinence to decision making**

CURRENT TRENDS IN CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR

The preceding historical perspective shows that successful companies adapt to changing consumer needs and environmental trends.

The late 1990s and early 2000s have seen equally important consumer behaviour trends that influence marketing strategies. A few particular are a greater value orientation on part of consumer, a desire for and access to more information, a more fragmented marketplace, an increase in time poverty, and desire for more customize products to fit consumer needs. The culmination of many of those trends is a greater consumer empowerment.

A greater value orientation:

Step recession is the early 1980s and 1990s and the economic downturn that started in 2000 have made consumer more price sensitive. Today, with the realization that growth is not unbundled and that there are limits to future purchasing power, consumer are viewing price more in the context of value, that is, getting one's money's worth. The emphasis on value has lead to a preponderance of "cross- shoppers"; that is, people who buy suits at Brooks cream and generic papers towels. This dichotomy makes sense to consumer seeing value at both high price ends and low price ends in certain product categories.

Greater interest in and access to information via the web:

More consumer than ever before have access to virtually unlimited information through the use of the internet. The greater incidences of home computers and advance in interactive technology have expanded the availability of product information in cyberspace. The strategic consequences of these changes on consumer behaviour are yet to be felt. It is likely that marketers will expand the range of product options available to consumer and ensure that fuller product information is provided than is now typically the case. Marketers will also consider a broader range of media option in communicating to consumer as well as broader range of delivery option.

Fragmentation of the marketplace:

Fragmentation has also occurred within segments defined by ethnic and national origin. The Hispanic market is no longer of as homogeneous. Companies have tried to appeal to more narrowly defined segments by adopting selective marketing messages to reach these audiences.

Increasing time poverty:

Consumers are busier than ever and now must face an ever-decreasing amount of free time. Time is divided not just between work and recreation, but also increasingly among family and community commitments. This means that consumers have less and less time to spend searching for information, shopping, and making purchase decisions. The implication is that marketers must emphasize service as well as price, using technology to reduce transaction time, building environments conducive to one-stop shopping, and adding value by providing fast and easy access to information.

A desire for more customized products:

The greater sophistication of consumer, their access to more information, and their emphasis on value has led them to desire products more closely fitted to their needs. Consumers today are looking for more option at lower prices. They want sneakers for different activities, snacks for different times of day, clothing that is custom-fitted, and cars with a specific set of option and accessories.

Because of this trend, some marketers believe that a totally new set of marketing strategies will arise in the future. Instead of product managers selling sell more customized products to

one consumer at a time. As the trend to customization accelerates, such strategies will become more feasible and likely.

Today, the **digital revolution** of the market place allows much greater customization of the products, services, and promotional messages than older marketing tools. By doing so, it enable marketers to build and maintain relationship with customers just like the sales person, grocer, and jeweller discussed earlier have done for many decades-but on a much greater and more efficient scale. Digital technologies also enable marketers to collect and analyze increasingly complex data on consumer's buying pattern and personal characteristic. On the other hand, the same technologies enable consumers to fine more information about products and services, including prices, more easily, efficiently, and for the most part, from the comfort of the own homes.

Over a period of a decade or so, the digital revolution has introduced drastic changes into the business environment:

Consumers have more power ever before. They can use “intelligent agents” to locate the best price for products or services, bid on various marketing offering, bypass distribution outlets and middlemen, and shop for goods around the globe and around the clock from the convenience of their homes.

Consumers have access to more information than ever before. They can easily find reviews for products they are considering buying that have been posted by previous buyers, click a button to compare the features of different product model at the site of online retailers, and subscribe, to “virtual communities” of person who share the same interests they do.

Marketers can offer more service and products than ever before. The digitization of information enables sellers to customize the products and services they are selling and still sell them at reasonable prices. It also allows marketers to customize the promotional messages directed at many customers.

The exchange between marketers and customer is increasingly interactive and instantaneous. Traditional advertising is one way street where the marketers pays a large sum of money to reach a large number of potential buyers via a mass medium, and then assesses whether or not the message was effective via future sales or market studies. On the other hand, digital communication enables a two-way interactive exchange in which consumers can instantly react to the marketer's message by, say, clicking on links within a

given web site or even by leaving the site. Thus, marketers can quickly gauge the effectiveness of their promotional message rather than rely on delay feedback through sales information that is collected after the fact.

Marketers can gather more information about consumers more quickly and easily. Marketers can track consumer's online behaviour and also gather information by requiring visitors to web sites to register and provide some information about themselves before they get access to the site's features. Thus, marketers can construct and update their consumer database efficiently and inexpensively.

Impact reaches beyond the PC-based connection to the web. Presently, most of the digital communication between consumers and marketers takes place via a PC connected to the web through a phone line, a cable modem, or another high speed connection. However, the digital revolution also gave us PDAs (personal digital assistants.) that are rapidly becoming connected to the web, often wirelessly. And it is likely that very soon our cell phones and PDAs will be combined into one product.

Consumer Behaviour and Marketing Action

Consumer behaviour is comparatively a new field of study which has evolved just after the Second World War. The sellers market has disappeared and buyers market has come up. This led to paradigm shift of the manufacture's attention from product to consumer and specially focused on the consumer behaviour.

The evaluation of marketing concept from mere selling concept to consumer- oriented marketing has resulted into buyer behaviour becoming an independent discipline. The growth of consumerism and consumer legislation emphasizes the importance that is given to the consumer.

Consumer behaviour is a study of how individuals make decision to spend their available resources (time, money and effort) or consumption related aspects (What they buy? When they buy? How they buy? etc.). The heterogeneity among people makes understanding consumer behaviour a challenging task to marketers.

Hence marketers felt the need to obtain an in-depth knowledge of consumers buying behaviour. Finally this knowledge acted as an imperative tool in the hands of marketers to

forecast the future buying behaviour of customers and devise four marketing strategies in order to create long term customer relationship.

CONSUMER INVOLVEMENT

Some consumers are characterized as being more involved in products and shopping than others. A consumer who is highly involved with a product would be interested in knowing a lot about it before purchasing. Hence he reads brochures thoroughly, compares brands and models available at different outlets, asks questions, and looks for recommendations. Thus consumer involvement can be defined as state of awareness that motivates consumers to seek out, attend to, and think about product information prior to purchase.

CAUSES OF CONSUMER INVOLVEMENT

The factors that influences consumer involvement include personal, product and situational.

PERSONAL FACTORS

Self-concept needs and values are the three personal factors that influence the extent of consumer involvement in a product or service. The more product image, the value symbolism inherent in it and the needs it serves are fitting together with the consumer self-image, values and needs, the more likely the consumer is to feel to be involved in it. Celebrities for example share a certain self-image, certain values, and certain needs. They tend to use products and services that reflect their life style. They get highly involved in purchasing prestigious products like designer wear, imported cars, health care products etc.

PRODUCT FACTORS

The consumer involvement grows as the level of perceived risk in the purchase of a good or service increases. It is likely that consumers will feel more involved in the purchase of their house than in the purchase of tooth paste, it is a more riskier purchase. Product differentiation affects involvement. The involvement increases as the number of alternatives that they have to choose from increases. This may be due to the fact that consumers feel variety which means greater risk. The pleasure one gets by using a product or service can also influence involvement. Some products are a greater source of pleasure to the consumer than others. Tea and coffee have a high level of hedonic (pleasure) value compared to, say household cleaners. Hence the involvement is high.

SITUATIONAL FACTORS

The situation in which the product is brought or used can generate emotional involvement. The reason for purchase or purchase occasion affects involvement. For example, buying a pair of socks for yourself is far less involved than buying a gift for a close friend. Social pressure can significantly increase involvement. One is likely to be more self conscious about the products and brands one looks at when shopping with friends than when shopping alone. The need to make a fast decision also influences involvement.

CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR MODELS

ECONOMIC OR MARSHALLIAN MODEL

This theory was first advanced by the economists. They gave formal explanation of buyer behaviour. According to this theory the consumers are assumed to be rational and conscious about economic calculations. They follow the law of marginal utility. An individual buyer seeks to spend his money on such goods which give maximum satisfaction (utility) according to his interests and at relative cost. The buying behaviour is determined by the income - its distribution and level-affects the purchasing power. The economic factors which affect the buyer's behaviour are:

DISPOSABLE PERSONAL INCOME

- Size of family income:
- Income Expectation:
- Tendency to Spend and to Save:
- Liquidity of Funds:
- consumer Credit:
- It is based on certain predictions of buying behaviour. They are:
- Lower the price of the product, higher the sales
- Lower the size of substitute product, lower the sale of this product
- Higher the real income, higher the sales of this product
- Higher the promotional expenses, higher will be the sales

LEARNING OR PAVLOVIAN MODEL

Psychology has contributed a lot to the marketers in understanding the buyers. It explains how consumers learn about a product and the way they can recall from the memory. and the development of buying habits. All theories of buyer's behaviour have been primarily based on learning, viz., Stimulation-Response or S-R model, this theory of learning is explained as a process of repetition. Motivation, conditioning and relationship. Repetition improves learning. For example. When advertisements are repeated, people may be able to understand further about the product. This is aimed at repeated advertisements for drawing the attention and interest of the people. According to stimulus-response theory learning involves the following steps.

- **Drive:** It is a strong internal stimulus which impels action and when it is directed towards a drive reducing object, it becomes a motive. A drive thus motivates a person for action to satisfy the need. Drives may be primary-thrust, hunger etc., and secondary -desire for money, pride etc.
- **Cues:** These are weak stimuli. They determine when the buyer will respond.
- **Response:** Response is the feedback reaction of the buyer. It is an answer given to drive or cue. The individual has to choose some specific response in order to fulfill the drive or the need which was acting as a stimulus. For example, a hunger drive can be satisfied by visiting a shop known through an advertisement and buying the readymade food product. If that experience is satisfactory, this response of satisfaction is strengthened.

- Learning refers to change in behaviour brought about by practice or experience. Everything one does or thinks is learnt.
- Product features such as price, quality, service, brand, and package etc., acts as cues or hints influencing consumer behaviour
- Marketing communications such as advertising, sales promotion etc., also act as guides Persuading buyer to purchase the product.
- Response is decision to purchase.

PSYCHOANALYTICAL MODEL

Sigmund Freud developed this theory. According to him human personality has three parts:

1. The Id, is the source of all mental energy that drives us to action
2. The super ego, the internal representation of what is social is approved Conscience
3. The Ego, the conscious director of id impulses for finding him satisfaction in socially acceptable manner.

The buyer behaviour depends upon the relative strength of the three elements in the personal ability. Motivational research has been involved in investigating motives of consumer behaviour so as to develop suitable marketing implications accordingly. This approach has been used to generate idea for developing-design, features, advertising and other promotional techniques.

SOCIOLOGICAL MODEL

According to this theory the individual decision and behaviour are quite often influenced by the family and the society. He gets influenced by it and in turn also influences it in its path of development. He plays many roles as a part of formal and informal associations or organizations i.e., as a family member, employee of a firm, member of professional forum, and as an active member of an informal cultural organization. Hence he is largely influenced by the group in which he is a member. For example, the decision may be made by one, actual buying may be done by another, and the product is used by yet another member of the family. Here, a mother takes a decision to buy a tiny cycle for her child, the cycle is purchased by the father and the user is the child.

HOWARD-SHETH MODEL

The Howard-Sheth model shows the processes and variables influencing the buyer behaviour before and during the purchase. It emphasizes three key variables-perception, learning and attitude formation. It explains the way consumers compare available products in order to choose the best which fits their needs and desires. Consumers learn by finding out the relevant information about products through two sources of information:

- Social sources
- Commercial sources

The gathered information is used for comparison of alternative brands according to various choice criteria. The basic structure of the model is given below :

Social Class, Financial Status

Exogenous Variable

Drive Stimuli Perception Learning Outputs

Basic Structure of Buying Behaviour

The following predictions can be made about the model

- Stimuli or perceived learning occurs and results in output.
- Output occurs on the basis of the perception and learning-non observable variables.
- Exogenous or outside variables such as social class, financial status etc., are used to predict perception and learning.

Black Box of Buys Behaviour

Howard - Sheth Brand Buyer Behaviour Model

Marketers must be aware of social environment and internal personal intertztzm1hfluencing the buyer behaviour.

Outside Variables:

- Personality

- Social Class
- Financial Status and Trial
- Culture
- Importance of Purchase
- Time Pressure

NICOSIA MODEL

Nicosia Model

The buyer behaviour model is taken from the marketing mans point of view. It is also called systems model as the human is analyzed as a system, with stimuli as the input to the system and the human behaviour as an output of the system.

Francesco Nicosia, an expert in consumer motivation and behaviour has developed this in 1966. He tried to explain buyer behaviour by establishing a link between the organization and its prospective consumer. The Nicosia model divides the above activity explanation into four basic areas:

The heterogeneity among people across the world makes understanding consumer buying behaviour an intricate and challenging task. Product motives and patronage motives play a crucial role in consumer purchases. Like individuals organizations also make many buying decisions. The major factors that distinguish it from consumer decision are Market structure and Demand, Buyer characteristics, and Decision process and buying patterns. The degree of involvement has a lot of impact on search of information, Information processing, and Transmission of information. The various models of consumer involvement help marketers to study purchase behaviour across product segments.

Consumers usually go through five stages in arriving at a purchase decision. In the first stage, the customer identifies an unsatisfied need. In the second stage consumer collect information about the product and brands. In a third stage, the consumer evaluates all the alternatives with the help of available information. Later in stage four, the customer makes a purchase decision. And finally in the fifth stage, consumer experiences post-purchase satisfaction or dissatisfaction.

As consumer behaviour is very complex to understand, consumer models aid marketer to put their effort to understand in right direction. The models-Economic. Learning, Psychoanalytic, sociological, Howard-Sheth and Nicosia enables marketers to understand and predict consumer behaviour in the market place.

INTERNET INFLUENCING THE CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR

The Net has virtually become a household name in India. This can be attributed to the growth of the private ISP market in the country, offering the cyber voyage at more and more

competitive prices. Internet in India is now one of the most vital mediums for information, entertainment and communication and the sole means for electronic commerce.

According to the India Internet Log Book 2000, India has over 1 million subscribers (and more than 5.5 million user) A closer look at the Internet user profile shows that 41 per cent are large, business firms who use the Net for their operations. Corporate India has realized the significance of e-commerce and the Net and has made it a part of its strategic planning exercise. Time and cost savings because of the disintermediation process further motivated large firms to embrace the Internet. SME (Small and Medium firms) accounted for 19 per cent of the user base, while the household segment accounted for 18 per cent. Education/research institutions and the government accounted for 10 percent and 12 percent respectively. As we had mentioned earlier, access to, rather than ownership of, the communication tool is important. It is not surprising to note that Internet usage is not just restricted to a single individual in a household or business. More than one family member in the Indian house-hold has used the Net for different needs. Research shows that the top Internet user is an adult son/daughter or male head of the family, thus adding up to 42 per cent of Net users in the age group of 15-24 years, 31 per cent in the 25-34 years age group, and the rest above 35 years, with a clear bias in favour of the male bread winner. Cyber cafés are most popular among the younger age groups of 16-20 years. 98 per cent of the times the Net is used for email; 93 per cent users use it for Web browsing, 59 per cent also engage in online chat and 55 per cent use it for information and data transfer. Only 6.5 per cent of net users engage in e-commerce. Figure and table gives details in this regard.

A direct implication of the above changes in consumer lifestyles has been that customer expectations from suppliers have gone up significantly. Today the customer's decision-making parameters are significantly different from those in earlier decades. Though an average Indian customer continues to be price sensitive, he is increasingly moving away from just low-priced product to quality products and services at the lowest prices. In other words, the Internet has created awareness among the Indian consumers about global quality and performance parameters that they can get an affordable price. The fact that an average consumer can buy a newly published book within a week directly from Amazon.com or a holiday from the best-known tour operator on his (customer's) term through the Net has put pressure on the Indian industry. Industry had to take another look at its costs, distribution models, and even input-output ratios. Competition further aggravated the scenario for most Indian companies, especially the older generation firms: One of the sectors where this change

was visible was the banking sector where new generation banks like HDFC and ICICI snatched the lead from nationalized banks, including the State Bank of India. HDFC Bank's leadership today is principally because it redefined banking paradigms for Indian consumers. It was the first to offer Net banking and several other services on the Net. This made banking convenient for the customer. The customer did not have to visit the bank but could do his/her transactions on the Net.

The Internet has made it possible for all market segments to have access to the same information and provide equal opportunity to all to buy products and services. Facilities like online chats have increasingly created customer communities which have, in a way, become pressure group. A company can no more hide poor performance or complaints in market from its customers in another. It is in this context that the Internet is a great leveler and facilitator that build relationships between s and sellers.

BUYING BEHAVIOUR

The buying behaviour of people is not applicable when a consumer buys an expensive product; it involves careful thinking and a large number of –to-participants. Buying day-to-day product like vegetables and groceries is different from buying an apartment or an automobile. Consumer buying behaviour is based on the degree of buyer involvement and the degree of differences, he perceives among brands.

Buying behaviour is the decision processes and acts of people/prospective customers involved in buying and using products, it helps in understanding:

- Why customers make the purchase that they make?
- What factors influence consumer purchase?
- The changing factors in our society.

Consumer buying behaviour refers to the buying behaviour of the ultimate consumer, a retailer needs to analyse buying behaviour for:

- Buyer's reaction to a retailer's marketing strategy has a great impact on a retailer's success.
- The marketing concept stresses that a retailer should create a marketing strategy that satisfies customers therefore need to analyse what, where, when and how consumer buy.

- Retailers can be better predicting how consumers will response to marketing strategies.

Extensive problem solving buying behaviour Consumer exhibits this type of behaviour when they indulge in buying expensive, infrequently purchased and unfamiliar products. It involves three stage processes.

1. Buyers develop a belief about the product.
2. Attitude is shaped around the belief.
3. The buyers make a well planned decision.

This type of decision making process calls for marketers to develop strategies that assist the customer to learn more about the product and the distinct features of their particular brand.

Reutilized buying behaviour

When customer buy low-cost, regularly purchased/routine products, they do they choose the brand, which they are familiar with or have been choosing for a long time. Purchase decision in such cases is quick.

Variety seeking behaviour

Consumer shows a great amount of differentiation when buying a low involvement product. They are not very brand conscious and often switch brand. For example in the case of toilet soap, only very few people stick to a particular brand while buying soaps. This is not due to dissatisfaction, but due to the need for variety. Purchase may base on the criteria like price, convenience, etc.

BUYING DECISION PROCESS: STAGES

Consumer passes through different stages before actually buying product. Data regarding theses stages in buying decision process can be obtained from the consumer who have already purchased the product or from prospective customer. Generally, the buying decision process can be divided in to five stages- problem recognition, information search, evaluation of alternatives, purchased decision and post purchase behaviour. All consumers may not go all of the five stages.

For e.g. Low involvement products that are frequently purchased do not need all the five stages of decision making processes but in case of less frequently purchased high price product or while buying the product or for the first time , the customer go through all the stages in the decision process. Sometimes, the change in product, price or even service might compel the customer to go through all the five stages of decision- making.

Problem recognition

The process of buying start when a person realizes that he has a problem or an unsatisfied need. A need can be aroused internally within the person, for example, hunger or buy n external stimulus. An external stimulus such as an advertisement or the attractiveness of a product package may also trigger a need in the person.

Information search

A consumer who realizes the need for a product will try to gather information regarding the product. Information search help the customer understand the features of a product and competing brands better. The information can be gathering from several sources like:

- Personal sources: family, friends, neighbours and reference group.

- Commercial sources: advertisement, internet and other marketing source
- Public sources: articles, newspaper, journals,
- Experiential sources: free trials, etc.

As the consumer gather more and more information about the product and brand and their features. After gathering information a customer than evaluate information.

Evaluation of alternatives

In this stage a customer analyses information available with him and select the right brand or product. The criteria of selecting are differ depending on the buying situation or in the level of involvement required. For a low involvement or low price product customer can use simple criteria, such as price. However infrequently purchased item or high price item, a customer can be involves detail analyses of information.

Purchased decision :Selection of a brand or purchased decision based on evaluation criteria and rating. The purchased decision also depends on availability of a brand. This stage involved major sub decision like,

- Seller and location of the store
- Time of purchased
- Size of the products, colours and attractiveness of the packaging
- Price of the product
- Delivery and warranty
- Payment method
- Ancillary service.

Post purchase behaviour

A customer evaluates the performance of a product after buying it. He will also compare the performance of a product with that of competitor's products. Consumer will be either satisfied or dissatisfied after evaluation. Buyer's post purchase feelings are important to marketers

Post purchase satisfaction: if the product meets the expected performance, the customer is satisfied. If the performance exceeds the expectation the customer is delighted and if it does not, the customer is dissatisfied. Marketers should try to improve product performance

and add new features and unique one to delight the customer. post purchased satisfaction with the product leads the customer to make repeat purchase and recommend it to others in his reference group.

Post purchase usage and disposal of the product is also of equal importance to the marketer, as it can save cost and time of producing as well as help in protecting the environmental equilibrium.

A MODEL OF CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR

As noted, the premise of this text is that marketing strategies consumer behaviour must be based on the factors that influence consumer behaviour. A simple model of consumer behaviour, emphasis the interaction between the marketer and the consumer. Consumer decision making- that is the process of perceiving and evaluating brand information, considering how brand alternatives meet the consumer's needs, and deciding on a brand- is the central component of the model.

Two broad influences determine the consumer's choice. The first is the individual consumer whose needs, perception of brand characteristics, and attitudes towards alternative influences brand choice. In addition, the consumer's demographics, lifestyle, and personality characteristic influences brand choice. The second influences on consumer decision making is the environment. The consumer's purchasing environment is represented by culture, subcultures, and face-to-face groups. Marketing organisations are also part of the consumer's environment, because these organisations provide the offering that can satisfy consumer needs.

Feedback to consumer

Post purchases evaluation

feedback to environment

word-of-mouth communication

Development of marketing strategies (part five)

Once the consumer has made a decision, post purchase evaluation, represented as feedback to the individual consumer, takes place. During evaluation, the consumer will learn from the experience and may change his or her pattern of acquiring information, evaluating brands, and selecting a brand. Consumption experience will directly influence whether the consumer will buy the same brand again. A feedback loop also leads to the environment. Consumers use word of mouth to communicate their purchase and consumption experience to friends and families.

Marketers seek information from consumer. They track consumer response in the form of market share and sales data. However, such information neither tells the marketer why the consumer purchased nor provides information on the strengths and weaknesses of the marketer's brand relative to those of the competition. Therefore, marketing research is also required at this step to determine consumer reaction to the brand and future purchase intent. This information permits management to reformulate marketing strategy to better meet consumer needs.

Marketers also seek information from the environment. They want to determine the nature of word-of-mouth communication regarding their brands. They also want to determine how cultural and social norms seek consumer opinions regarding their corporate image in the context of social responsibility.

TYPES OF CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR

There are four types of consumer choice processes based on the level of involvement and decision making: complex decision making, brand loyalty, inertia, and limited decision making. The high- and – low involvement processes are described by different learning theories based on these decision hierarchies.

Complex decision making and brand loyalty:

The upper left- hand box represents the process of complex decision making described by the traditional 'think-before-you-act' hierarchy. The learning theory that best described this process is cognitive learning; that is, a process that requires the consumer's development of brand loyalty attitudes and a detailed evaluation of brand alternatives.

The lower left-hand box described loyalty, that is, consumers make purchases with little deliberation because of past satisfaction and a strong commitment to the brand as a result. The web offers consumer the ability to save time by purchasing a known brand online. Additionally, consumer can develop customized specification for purchasing a known brand, for example Dell computers. The learning theory that best described brand loyalty is instrumental conditioning. Both high-involvement processes are described by a beliefs/evaluation/behaviour hierarchy; expect that forming beliefs and evaluating brands are not a necessary part of the choice process in brand loyalty.

Inertia: The lower right-hand box represents the Morton salt example buying based on inertia. As we saw, when a low-involvement hierarchy operates, a consumer forms beliefs passively, makes a decision with little information processing, and then evaluates the brand after the purchase. Because inertia involves repetitive buying of the same brand to avoid making a decision, the consumer does not make a subsequent brand evaluation until after the first purchase. If the brand achieves a certain minimum level of satisfaction, the consumer will repurchase it on a routinized basis. This process is some times referred to as spurious loyalty because repetitive purchase may make it appear that the consumer is loyal to the brand when actually no such loyalty exists.

The learning theory that best described inertia is classical conditioning. When the consumer is not involved with the product, contiguity between a stimulus and a response could be established more easily through repetitive advertising because the consumer is in a passive

state. The consumer forms the association without thinking. When the consumer goes into a store, the association may be triggered by seeing the product; and the easiest thing to do is to buy the product with little deliberation. Thus, repetitive exposure to a theme like ‘the quicker picker upper’ for Bounty paper towels might create an association between absorbency and the product for a low-involvement product category

Limited decision making:

Occasionally, low-involvement purchase warrant some decision making in contrast to the process of routinized decision making that characterizes inertia. The introduction of a new product, a change in the existing brand, or a desire for variety might cause a consumer to switch from routinized to limited decision making. . The decision process conforms to a low-involvement hierarchy, as there is little information seeking and brand evaluation. The consumer forms beliefs about the brand, purchases the brand, and then evaluates it based on initial trial.

Although limited decision making involves cognitive processes, the relevant learning process is described as passive rather than cognitive learning, because no active information search and brand evaluation takes place. The consumer receives information about the new paper towel passively and puts it in the back of his or her mind. Seeing the brand in the store triggers recall; the consumer examines the package and purchases the product for trial.

Information search engines on the web may encourage limited decision making by minimizing the time required to find the right product for a particular need. A consumer looking for advice on removing a paint stain might not be particularly involved with the subject and uses google.com to quickly determine the relevant site and information for the purpose. Such efficient information search is a prime advantage of the web in low-involvement conditions.

An important form of limited decision making is variety seeking. Consumers often try a variety of brands out of boredom simply because many low-involvement products are ordinary and mundane. One study found that under these conditions, consumers often switch to a less preferred brand just to experience variety of alternatives.

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